

**INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**
[ISSN: 0975-4725; CODEN(USA): IJPS00]
Journal Homepage: <https://www.ijpsjournal.com>

Research Article

Development and Validation of a New Reverse Phase - High Performance Liquid Chromatography Method for Quantification of Imeglimin Hydrochloride

Shahed Shaikh*, Preeti Sable, Sushama Vaishnav, Pravin Wakte

Department of Chemical Technology, Dr Babasaheb Ambedkar Marathwada University, Chhatrapati Sambhajinagar 431004

ARTICLE INFO

Published: 25 Oct 2025

Keywords:

Quantification, Imeglimin Hydrochloride, RP-HPLC Method Development, Validation.

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.17442583

ABSTRACT

Imeglimin Hydrochloride, a novel oral antidiabetic drug belonging to the 'glimin' class, has shown promising results in the treatment of type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM). A rapid, simple, and validated reversed-phase high-performance liquid chromatography (RP-HPLC) method was developed for the quantification of Imeglimin Hydrochloride in bulk and tablet dosage forms. The method employed a Shimadzu C18 (150 x 4.6 mm, 5 µm) with an isocratic mobile phase of Methanol : OPA buffer (0.05%) in the ratio of 55:45 v/v at a flow rate of 1.0 mL/min. Detection was performed at 240 nm, and the retention time was observed at 3.728 minutes. The method was validated according to ICH Q2(R1) guidelines for parameters including specificity, linearity, accuracy, precision, robustness, limit of detection (LOD), and limit of quantification (LOQ). Linearity was established in the range of 5–25 µg/mL ($R^2 = 0.9909$). LOD and LOQ were found to be 0.02 µg/mL and 0.05 µg/mL, respectively. The method proved to be accurate (mean recovery 99.90% to 101.63%) and precise (RSD < 2%). This validated method can be applied for routine quality control analysis of Imeglimin Hydrochloride in pharmaceutical dosage forms.

INTRODUCTION

Imeglimin Hydrochloride is the first tetrahydro-triazine-containing antidiabetic drug to receive approval. It enhances glucose uptake in skeletal muscle, restores insulin secretion, and improves

mitochondrial function [1, 2]. Chemically, it is (6R)-(+)-4-dimethylamino-2-imino-6-methyl-1,2,5,6-tetrahydro-1,3,5-triazine hydrochloride, with a molecular weight of 191.66 g/mol, Melting Point of 223-225°C, with pKa Value of 10.21. Imeglimin hydrochloride is soluble in organic

*Corresponding Author: Shahed Shaikh

Address: Department of Chemical Technology, Dr Babasaheb Ambedkar Marathwada University, Chhatrapati Sambhajinagar 431004

Email ✉: shaikhshahed8786@gmail.com

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

solvent such as ethanol, Dimethyl Sulfoxide (DMSO) and methanol. Freely soluble in acetone, sparingly soluble in ethyl acetate [3].

Figure 1 Chemical Structure of Imeglimin Hydrochloride

Imeglimin hydrochloride has been accepted as a beneficial oral antidiabetic agent [4]. The increasing use of Imeglimin hydrochloride in the market has led to the need for more efficient and rapid analytical methods [5, 6, 7]. Method development involves designing an analytical procedure tailored for a specific application, whereas method validation confirms that the developed procedure performs reliably and is appropriate for its intended analytical purpose [8, 9]. Among the available analytical techniques, HPLC remains the gold standard due to its sensitivity, reproducibility, and precision [10, 11]. The objective of the present work was to develop and validate a RP-HPLC method for the quantification of Imeglimin Hydrochloride in bulk and tablet dosage forms, in accordance with ICH guidelines [12]. The developed method will be helpful for other researchers and manufacturers.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Chemicals and reagent:

Imeglimin Hydrochloride API was obtained by Alkem Private Ltd. Mumbai. Imeglimin Hydrochloride 500 mg tablet of Zyuds Healthcare Ltd. Purchased from local vendor. HPLC grade

Methanol and Water were procured from Merck, Ortho-Phosphoric acid (OPA) from Rankem.

Instrumentation:

The analysis was carried out on a Shimadzu Quaternary gradient HPLC system (P-Series) HPLC system equipped with an Shimadzu SPD-M40 Photodiode Array Detector and Manual injector (20 μ L loop). Data acquisition was performed using Lab Solution (Version DB 6.110) software. A UV-Visible spectrophotometer (Shimadzu: 1780 Double Beam Spectrophotometers) was used to determine the λ_{max} . Analytical Balance (Shimadzu Model: AUW220D) and Bath Ultrasonicator (Model 5.5L-150H).

Chromatographic conditions:

Table 1: Optimised Chromatographic Conditions

Separation variable	Optimized conditions
Mobile Phase	Methanol : OPA buffer (0.05%) (55:45 v/v)
Column	Shimadzu C18 (150 x 4.6 mm, 5 μ m)
Detector	Shimadzu SPD-M40 Photodiode Array
Software	Lab Solution (Version DB 6.110)
Detection Wavelength	240 nm
Flow Rate	1.0 mL/min
Injection Volume	20 μ L
Temperature	20°C
Type of elution	Isocratic
Run time	15 min
Retention time	3.728

Preparation of OPA (0.5%) buffer:

Accurately measured 0.5 mL of ortho-phosphoric acid (OPA) was transferred into a 100 mL volumetric flask, and the volume was made up to the mark with HPLC-grade water. The solution was then sonicated for 20 minutes to ensure proper mixing and degassing.

Preparation of mobile phase:

The working mobile phase was prepared by mixing Methanol and 0.5% Ortho-phosphoric acid (OPA) buffer in a ratio of 55:45 (v/v).

Preparation of standard solutions (1000 µg/ml):

Accurately weighed 10 mg of Imeglimin Hydrochloride was transferred into a 10 mL volumetric flask, dissolved in a small quantity of mobile phase, and the volume was made up to the mark with the same mobile phase. The prepared stock solution was filtered via a 0.45 µm nylon membrane syringe filter.

Working Solutions for Calibration (5–25 µg/mL):

From the above stock solution, 1 mL was transferred into a 10 mL volumetric flask and diluted to volume with the mobile phase to obtain a working solution of 100 µg/mL. From this working solution, aliquots of 0.5, 1.0, 1.5, 2.0, and 2.5 mL were transferred into separate 10 mL volumetric flasks and diluted to volume with the mobile phase to yield calibration standards of 5, 10, 15, 20, and 25 µg/mL, respectively.

Preparation of sample solutions:

Ten tablets of Imeglimin Hydrochloride (500 mg) were weighed, triturated, and a portion equivalent to 50 mg of the drug was dissolved in 25 mL mobile phase, sonicated for 15 minutes, and made up to 50 mL with the mobile phase (final concentration: 1000 µg/mL). Appropriate dilutions were made for analysis.

Method validation:

The method was validated according to the International Conference on Harmonisation (ICH) guidelines Q2(R1).

Accuracy

Accuracy represents how close the experimental results are to the true or reference values. Accuracy of the method was obtained by performing recovery studies by the standard addition method at different levels of pure standard drug i.e., 80%, 100% and 120% of Imeglimin Hydrochloride, to previously analyzed tablet powder sample and mixtures were reanalyzed by the proposed method. From the amount of drug found percentage recovery was calculated [13].

Precision

The precision of the developed analytical method was evaluated through intra-day (repeatability) and inter-day (intermediate) studies. Repeatability was assessed by analyzing three concentrations of the drug three times within the same day (morning, afternoon, and evening). Inter-day precision was determined by analyzing the same concentrations on three consecutive days. The results of both intra-day and inter-day studies were expressed as percentage relative standard deviation (%RSD) [14].

Linearity

Linearity evaluates whether the analytical signal shows a proportional increase with the analyte concentration across the studied range [15]. The linearity of the method was evaluated by constructing a calibration curve for Imeglimin Hydrochloride in the concentration range of 5–25 µg/mL. Peak area was plotted against concentration for each calibration standard, and linear regression analysis was performed to assess linearity.

Specificity

The specificity of method was determined by comparing the chromatogram obtained from bulk

drug with that of marketed formulation no excipients interference was found, thus method was found to be specific [16].

Limit of Detection (LOD) and Limit of Quantification (LOQ)

The Limit of Detection (LOD) refers to the smallest concentration of analyte that can be identified, though not quantified with precision, The LOD was calculated as

$$\text{LOD} = 3.3 \times \frac{\text{Standard Deviation of Y – intercept}}{\text{Average slope of six calibration curves}}$$

Whereas the smallest amount of sample that can be accurately quantified is known as the Limit of Quantification (LOQ). The LOQ was calculated as

$$\text{LOQ} = 10 \times \frac{\text{Standard Deviation of Y – intercept}}{\text{Average slope of six calibration curves}}$$

Robustness

Robustness was assessed by evaluating the method's consistency under routine conditions and after introducing small deliberate variations in parameters like flow rate, pH, and detection wavelength. Robustness was assessed using the % RSD and the percent recovery [17, 18].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Several mobile phase compositions were investigated, including Methanol: 0.5% OPA in ratios of 80:20, 75:25, 70:30, 60:40, and 55:45 (v/v), at different wavelengths based on the literature survey. Imeglimin Hydrochloride was found to be soluble in organic solvents such as methanol, acetonitrile, DMSO, and water. Considering solubility and chromatographic performance, the final method was developed using Methanol: 0.5% OPA (55:45, v/v) as the mobile phase, with the same composition used as diluent.

Trials on different compositions:

Figure 2 Chromatogram of Trial

Remarks: Peak shape was not proper; method was not found suitable.

Figure 3 Chromatogram of selected method

Ret. Time	Area	Height	NTP(USP)	HETP(USP)	Tailing F.
3.738	1113737	163235	5705	26.294	1.273

Remarks: In this trial the retention time of Imeglimin Hydrochloride was observed at 3.738 min and peak was sharp, well-shaped and symmetrical using this system. Hence this trial considered as optimized trial from all the trial for further analysis.

Imeglimin Hydrochloride in the range of 5 - 25 μ g/ml. The regression equation for the calibration curve of Imeglimin Hydrochloride was found to be $r^2 = 0.9909$. A linear relationship was observed between concentration and response for the drug. The regression equation was,

$$y = 56678x + 651929$$

$$R^2 = 0.9909$$

METHOD VALIDATION

Linearity:

The calibration curves were plotted for each concentration range. Linearity was determined for

Linearity Study

Table 2 Linearity of Imeglimin Hydrochloride

Sr No.	Conc. (μ g/ml)	AUC-1	AUC 2	AUC 3	Average	SD	% RSD
1	5	986299	986385	986531	986405.000	117.2860	0.01189
2	10	1161657	1161876	1161987	1161840.000	167.9196	0.014453
3	15	1495973	1494988	1495839	1495600.000	534.2256	0.03572
4	20	1764171	1765005	1764982	1764719.333	475.0098	0.02692
5	25	2101863	2101965	2101898	2101908.667	51.8298	0.00247
Average %RSD = 0.01829							

Calibration curve for Imeglimin Hydrochloride.

Figure 4 Chromatogram of Imeglimin HCl for linearity at Concentration 05 $\mu\text{g/ml}$.

Figure 5 Chromatogram of Imeglimin HCl for linearity at Concentration 10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$.

Figure 6 Chromatogram of Imeglimin HCl for linearity at Concentration 15 µg/ml

Figure 7 Chromatogram of Imeglimin HCl for linearity at Concentration 20 µg/ml

Figure 8 Chromatogram of Imeglimin HCl for linearity at Concentration 25 µg/ml

Limit of detection and limit of quantification:

LOD = 3.3 SD/D

LOQ = 10 SD/D

The LOD and LOQ of Imeglimin Hydrochloride by the proposed methods were determined using Calibration standards. LOD and LOQ values were calculated as 3.3 SD/d and 10 SD/d respectively, where d is the slope of the calibration curve and SD is the standard deviation.

Where,

D = slope of the calibration curve

SD= standard deviation

LOD	LOQ
0.02 µg/mL	0.05 µg/mL

Robustness:

The robustness study results were within the acceptance range represented in table 3 and 4 indicated the samples solution 10 µg/ml shows the correct AUC, number of theoretical plate (NTP), Height equivalent to theoretical plate (HETP) and retention time by using two variable like Change in flow rate and change in wavelength, The robustness study was carried out by determining effect of small variation in Change in wavelength

(238 nm & 242 nm) i.e., + 2 nm: Change in flow rate i.e., ± 0.1 ml/min (0.9 ml/min & 1.1 ml/min).

Table 3 Robustness change in wavelength.

Change in wavelength	238	240	242
AUC	1141452	1141432	1141475
NTP	6074	6080	6068
HETP	24.695	24.698	24.688

Chromatogram of change in wavelength (± 2nm).

Figure 9 Chromatogram of Imeglimin HCl for robustness at wavelength 238nm (-2nm)

Figure 10 Chromatogram of Imeglimin HCl for robustness at wavelength 242nm (+ 2nm)

Change in flow rate (0.9 ml/min & 1.1 ml/min).

Table 4 Robustness Change in flow rate at 0.9 ml/min and 1.1 ml/min.

Change in wavelength	1 ml	0.9 ml	1.1 ml
AUC	1141452	1141439	1141461
NTP	6074	6073	6076
HETP	24.695	24.701	24.683

Figure 11 Chromatogram of Imeglimin HCl for robustness at flow rate 0.9 ml/min (-0.1ml/min).

Figure 12 Chromatogram of Imeglimin HCl for robustness at flow rate 1.1 ml/min (+ 0.1ml/min).

Precision:

1. Intra-day:

The intra-day and inter-day precision study as showed in Table 5 and 6 of the developed method confirmed adequate sample stability and method reliability where all the RSDs were < 2%.

Time 10:00 am, 2:00 pm and 5:00 pm.

Table 5 Intraday precision at time 10:00 am, 2:00 pm, 5:00 pm.

Conc. In µg/ml	AUC			Mean	SD	% RSD
	10:00 AM	2:00 PM	5:00 PM			
10	1141452	1141446	1141450	1141449.333	3.055	0.000
15	1495973	1495978	1495971	1495974.000	3.606	0.000
20	1764171	1764163	1764167	1764167.000	4.000	0.000
				Average RSD		0.000245

2. Inter-day:

Table 6 Inter day precision at three different days.

Conc. in µg/ml	AUC			Mean	SD	% RSD
	DAY 1	DAY 2	DAY 3			
10	1141452	1141461	1141411	1141441.333	26.652	0.002
15	1495973	1495967	1495964	1495968.000	4.583	0.000
20	1764171	1764169	1764165	1764168.333	3.055	0.000
				Average RSD		0.000938

Accuracy:

Accuracy of the method was obtained by performing recovery studies by the standard addition method (Spiking) at different levels of

pure standard drug i.e., 80%, 100% and 120% of Imeglimin Hydrochloride. From the amount of drug found percentage recovery was calculated. Results within the range of 99.90–101.63 % ensure an accurate method given in table 7.

Table 7 Accuracy of Imeglimin HCl at the spiking of 80, 100, and 120% for concentration of 10, 15, 20 µg/ml

Sr. No.	Drug Conc. (µg/ml)	Addition (µg/ml)	spike solution (µg/ml)	AUC of STD Solution	AUC of spike solution	Average AUC of spike solution	Average Spike Solution Recovery	% Recovery	SD	% RSD
1	10	8	18	1141452	2054613	2054439	17.99848	99.99	205.679 3621	0.0100 11
2	10	10	20	1141446	2282904	2315279	20.28363	101.42	56837.8 0334	2.4549 01
3	10	12	22	1141450	2511194	2511171	21.9998	100.00	55.1935 9866	0.0021 98
4	15	12	27	1495973	2692654	2693660	27.01009	100.04	120.253 8981	0.0044 64
5	15	15	30	1495978	2991946	3040654	30.48839	101.63	35276.0 1921	1.1601 46
6	15	18	33	1495971	3291140	3325848	33.34801	101.05	57576.2 7617	1.7311 76
7	20	16	36	1764171	2095507	2095442	35.99888	100.00	3553.51 5302	0.1695 83
8	20	20	40	1764163	2328342	2325907	39.95817	99.90	4249.28 088	0.1826 93
9	20	24	44	1764167	2561176	2561216	44.00069	100.00	37.8065 2501	0.0014 76

Figure 13 Chromatogram of Accuracy of method using 10 µg/ml with Spike Concentration 80%

Figure 14 Chromatogram of Accuracy of method using 10 µg/ml with Spike Concentration 100%

Figure 15 Chromatogram of Accuracy of method using 10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ with Spike Concentration 120%

Figure 16 Chromatogram of Accuracy of method using 15 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ with Spike Concentration 80%

Figure 17 Chromatogram of Accuracy of method using 15 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ with Spike Concentration 100%

Figure 18 Chromatogram of Accuracy of method using 15 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ with Spike Concentration 120%

Figure 19 Chromatogram of Accuracy of method using 20 µg/ml with Spike Concentration 80%

Figure 20 Chromatogram of Accuracy of method using 20 µg/ml with Spike Concentration 100%

Figure 21 Chromatogram of Accuracy of method using 20 µg/ml with Spike Concentration 120%

Table 8 Summary of validation parameter by HPLC.

Parameter	Data for Imeglimin Hcl
Linearity	5 - 25 µg
Line of Correlation	$y = 57083x + 641807$
Regression Coefficient (R ²)	0.9909
Retention time	3.728 min
Limit of Detection (µg/ml)	0.02 µg/mL
Limit of Quantification (µg/ml)	0.05 µg/mL
Accuracy (% Mean recovery)	100%
Intra-day precision (%RSD)	10 µg/ml = 0.00% 15 µg/ml = 0.00% 20 µg/ml = 0.00%

Inter-day precision (%RSD)	10 µg/ml = 0.02% 15 µg/ml = 0.00% 20 µg/ml = 0.00%
Robustness	Robust
System suitability	System suitable

The developed method provided a sharp and symmetrical peak for Imeglimin Hydrochloride with a retention time of 3.728 minutes, demonstrating rapid elution compared to reported methods. The system suitability parameters including theoretical plates (>2000) and tailing factor (<2) confirmed the efficiency of the chromatographic system.

Linearity was established in the concentration range of 0.5 - 25 µg/mL with an excellent correlation coefficient ($R^2 = 0.9909$), indicating the method's suitability for quantitative applications. Precision studies demonstrated %RSD values of 0.000245% (intra-day) and 0.000938% (inter-day), well within the acceptance limits (<2%).

Accuracy was validated by recovery studies at three different concentration levels, yielding recoveries between 99.90% and 101.63%, confirming that the method is accurate. LOD and LOQ values of 0.02 µg/mL and 0.05 µg/mL, respectively, indicate the high sensitivity of the method.

Robustness testing under minor deliberate variations in flow rate and wavelength showed no significant changes in retention time or peak area, proving the reliability of the method for routine analysis. Overall, the developed method is rapid, sensitive, and highly reproducible, making it suitable for quality control of bulk and formulated Imeglimin Hydrochloride.

CONCLUSION

A simple, rapid, and validated RP-HPLC method was successfully developed for the quantification of Imeglimin Hydrochloride in bulk and tablet dosage forms. The method met all validation parameters as per ICH Q2(R1) guidelines, proving to be specific, precise, accurate, sensitive, and robust. Its short run time and high sensitivity make it advantageous for routine quality control and stability studies of Imeglimin Hydrochloride.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The authors are thankful to the University Department of Chemical Technology and Y.B. Chavan College of Pharmacy, Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar Marathwada University, Aurangabad, Maharashtra, for providing the laboratory facilities and instrumentation support to carry out this research work. The authors also extend their gratitude to Alkem Private Ltd., Mumbai, for kindly providing the Imeglimin Hydrochloride API sample.

Author Contributions

- Shahed Shaikh: Conceptualization, Method Development, Validation, Writing – Original Draft.
- Preeti Sable: Supervision, Data Analysis, Manuscript Editing.
- Sushama Vaishnav: Methodology Guidance, Critical Review.
- Pravin Wakte: Provide Resources, Final Approval of Manuscript.

Funding: This research received no external funding.

Data Availability Statement: All data generated or analyzed during this study are included in this published article.

REFERENCES

1. Hallakou-Bozec S, Vial G, Kergoat M, Fouqueray P, Bolze S, Borel AL, et al. Mechanism of action of Imeglimin: A novel therapeutic agent for type 2 diabetes. *Diabetes Obes Metab.* 2021;23(3):664-673.
2. Dubourg J, Fouqueray P, Thang C, et al. Imeglimin exerts its effects via a distinct mode of action involving mitochondrial function. *Br J Pharmacol.* 2021;178(9):2063-2076.
3. Navali S, Lalitha N, Mubeen G. RP-HPLC Method for Determination of Imeglimin Hydrochloride in Bulk and Tablet Formulation. *Asian J Pharm Res Dev.* 2024;12(4):92-96. doi:10.22270/ajprd.v12i4.1446.
4. Pirags V, Lebovitz H, Fouqueray P. Imeglimin, a novel glimin oral antidiabetic, exhibits a good efficacy and safety profile in type 2 diabetic patients. *Diabetes Obes Metab.* 2012;14(9):852-858.
5. Kadambari S. Wagh, Tejashri R. Dugaje, Priyanka B. Jadhav, Chetna Y. Gavitt, Revati A. Khairnar. Analytical Methods for Imeglimin Hydrochloride: A Comprehensive Review of Current Approaches and Advances. *International Journal for Research in Applied Science & Engineering Technology (IJRASET)*. ISSN: 2321-9653; Volume 13 Issue III Mar 2025.
6. Patel RM, Patel NJ. Development and validation of analytical methods by RP-HPLC for pharmaceutical drugs. *J Pharm Anal.* 2021;11(5):529-540.
7. Earla R, Thakkar A, Shah RP, et al. Analytical method development and validation for pharmaceutical applications: An overview. *Crit Rev Anal Chem.* 2018;48(5):309-322.
8. Mossammat Rima Akter, Md. Saddam Hossain, K M Khairul Alam and Md Rafiquzzaman. Development and Validation of RP-HPLC Method for the Determination of Anticancer Drug Brigatinib. *GSC Biological and Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 2023, 23(03), 030-041.
9. Blessy M, Patel RD, Prajapati PN, Agrawal YK. Development of forced degradation and stability indicating methods: A critical review. *J Pharm Anal.* 2014;4(3):159-165.
10. Snyder LR, Kirkland JJ, Dolan JW. *Introduction to Modern Liquid Chromatography*. 3rd ed. Wiley; 2010.
11. Kumar A, Nalli Y, Joshi H. RP-HPLC Method Development and Validation: Recent Trends and Challenges. *Curr Pharm Anal.* 2022;18(4):325-335.
12. ICH Harmonised Tripartite Guideline Q2(R1): Validation of Analytical Procedures: Text and Methodology. International Conference on Harmonisation, 2005.
13. Ajay SS, Mohini SK, Lahu DH. Development and Validation of RP-HPLC Method for Estimation of Anti-Diabetic Drug in Bulk and Tablet Dosage Form. *Int J Pharm Sci.* 2023;10(5):366-378.
14. Clémence C, Fouqueray P, Sébastien B. Pharmacokinetics and disposition of Imeglimin in preclinical species and humans. *Drug Metab Dispos.* 2020;48(12):1330-1346.
15. Nikam K, Bhusari S, Wakte P. High-Performance Liquid Chromatography Method Development and Validation for Estimation of Mahanimbine in Curry Leaves. *Indian J of Pharmaceutical Education and Research.* 2024;58(1s):s217-s223.

16. FDA Guidance for Industry. Bioanalytical Method Validation. U.S. Food and Drug Administration, 2018.
17. Shrivastava A, Gupta VB. Methods for the determination of limit of detection and limit of quantitation of the analytical methods. *Chron Young Sci.* 2011;2(1):21-25.
18. Bakshi M, Singh S. Development of validated stability-indicating assays–critical review. *J Pharm Biomed Anal.* 2002;28(6):1011–1040.

HOW TO CITE: Shahed Shaikh, Preeti Sable, Sushama Vaishnav, Pravin Wakte, Development and Validation of a New Reverse Phase - High Performance Liquid Chromatography Method for Quantification of Imeglimin Hydrochloride, *Int. J. of Pharm. Sci.*, 2025, Vol 3, Issue 10, 2719-2733. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17442583>